

TRANSIENCE

**TRANSITIONING TOWARDS AN EFFICIENT,
CARBON-NEUTRAL CIRCULAR EUROPEAN
INDUSTRY**

Date: 22/04/2024

D5.1 – VISUAL IDENTITY & WEBSITE

WP5 – Setting up communication,
dissemination, networking

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable constitutes a reference document available to the consortium partners to showcase the development and design of the project's visual identity and other relevant specifications required for creating communication and dissemination materials for all purposes. The deliverable also describes and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the TRANSCIENCE project website.

This document can also be used by policymakers and industry stakeholders as a documentation of the visual identity of the TRANSCIENCE project as well as a reference material for research projects seeking to explore options and ideas for an efficient dissemination strategy through a website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The TRANSCIENCE visual identity will, according to the DoA, be used to develop Word and PowerPoint templates as well as communication materials such as flyers, project presentations and posters, and the project website, in a distinctive and attractive manner based on the project's objectives and target audiences.

The TRANSCIENCE website aims to constitute a constant node of dissemination and engagement and a reference site with materials (deliverables, visuals, briefs, papers, etc.) and useful links related to industrial decarbonisation, circularity performance and overall sustainability, and the EU's transition to net-zero, as well as to relevant initiatives, actors, consortia, and projects. The website will also feature information on the concept, work structure, consortium, scientific advisory board, synergies, model frameworks, news, and events of the TRANSCIENCE project, including information on the MIC3 model ecosystem.

This report presents in detail the visual identity of the project and provides a description of the website's design, development process, and structure. It contains all promotional visual identity material as well as reference screenshots of the website's main sections and features. It also showcases the website's ambition to serve as a one-stop-shop portal providing all project related information, materials, and results.

All visual identity and website materials presented will be updated along the project's progress.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report and the project's website, which can be accessed at <https://www.transience.eu/> as well as at <https://www.industry4netzero.eu>.

Preface

The need to approach climate action, resource efficiency, and circularity performance as integrated, economy-wide, cross-cutting issues is growingly gaining attention in the policy world, stimulating the development of new industrial policies in Europe and worldwide. Currently, however, there is little progress in conceptualising the circular economy and understanding its interactions with climate action. State-of-the-art modelling capacity to capture the interplay of the two agendas and their implications for energy-intensive sectors as well as to represent the European industry's transformation in line with the region's vision for climate neutrality is not yet fully developed. TRANSIENCE will undertake a comprehensive characterisation and assessment of circularity principles and measures vis-à-vis decarbonisation, by looking at the twin transition of European industries through the lenses of global competitiveness, innovation, and holistic sustainability. It will then produce MIC3, a consistent, fully open-source model ecosystem to assess industrial circularity, decarbonisation, and sustainability. A series of interoperable modules on the socioeconomic, service and product, material, industrial, energy-system, and environmental perspectives of the transformation of European industry will be developed and integrated, building on and opening the code of leading modelling tools. MIC3 will finally be used in extensive scenario modelling to produce diverse pathways toward a material-efficient, circular, climate-neutral, sustainable European industry. Transparency, openness, and knowledge sharing will be promoted, and technical capacities will be developed in four industrial agglomerations in the EU, moving beyond stakeholder consultation, onto model co-development, continuous validation of assumptions, co-creation of scenario modelling, evaluation of the desirability and usability of the developed model and insights, and eventually co-production of science and action.

ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	EL	
CEPS – Centre for European Policy Studies	BE	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	EL	
Fraunhofer – Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung Ev	DE	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
PIK – Potsdam Institut Fur Klimafolgenforschung Ev	DE	
PNTEC – Park Naukowo-Technologiczny Euro-Centrum Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia	PL	
TECNALIA – Fundacion Tecnalía Research & Innovation	ES	
UU – Universiteit Utrecht	NL	
WI – Wuppertal Institut Fur Klima, Umwelt, Energie GGMBH	DE	
PSI – Paul Scherrer Institut	CH	
UCL – University College London	UK	

Executive Summary

This report accompanies and documents the design, implementation, and deployment of the TRANSIENCE project visual identity and website.

Apart from the project logo, the TRANSIENCE visual identity consists of a flyer to create visibility (in English and partners' languages); a leaflet for dissemination on objectives, methods, and expected results (in English and partners' languages); a poster template for physical/online events organised by partners or relevant organisations as promotional material, a roll-up banner for policy or industry events, and a template presentation with basic project information to be regularly updated and adapted to event and audience.

The TRANSIENCE website can be found at the following two addresses: <https://transience.eu/>, and <https://industry4netzero.eu/>. Designed based on the most recent practices and principles for web design, the TRANSIENCE website follows a modern, industry-facing, and user-friendly approach showcasing the project's concept and objectives in detail, containing project-relevant material, and notably featuring one dedicated section for news and events and one for the project's key output: the MIC3 framework.

The purpose of this document is to describe the visual identity and website of the TRANSIENCE project, which is part of Task 5.1 "TRANSIENCE visual identity & website". The communication and dissemination materials presented here include the project's logo, flyer, leaflet, poster, roll-up banner, template project presentation, and indicative examples of the website's content (in screenshots).

The project's website and visual identity will be constantly updated along the project's progression, facilitating stakeholder engagement as well as engagement with the general public, demonstrating project results, publications, news, events, and expecting the partners' participation as well as interactions with related synergy projects and the broader scientific community, until the completion of the project.

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1 TRANSIENCE Visual Identity

1.1 The importance of a Visual Identity

It is important to establish an attractive and distinctive visual identity early on, based on the project's objectives and target stakeholder groups. The TRANSIENCE visual identity conveys what the project is about, through applications such as the final logo and graphical charter; a flyer to create visibility (in English and in partners' languages); a leaflet for dissemination on objectives, methods, and expected results (in English and in partners' languages); a poster template for physical and/or online events organised by consortium partners or relevant organisations as promotional material; a roll-up banner for policy and/or industry events; and a template presentation with basic project information to be regularly updated and appropriately adapted to any given event and audience.

The TRANSIENCE visual identity comprises the colour palette and design elements that distinguish the project in all its promotional materials, as well as the project's presentations and reports. It aims to convey the project's scope, objectives, and outcomes in a unified and integrated manner.

1.2 Structure of the TRANSIENCE Visual Identity

The structure of the TRANSIENCE visual identity has been designed to correspond to the project's concept, including elements and features that relate to its industry-facing orientation. The circular shape used for the final logo, represents the project's open, integrated, and participatory aspects, and conveys the circularity principle guiding the industrial transition.

A transient colour palette is insightfully chosen for the final logo. Three main colours are selected. First, dark green, which is strongly associated with nature, plants, and the environment; it is also the colour that is mostly used to address environmental initiatives and climate action and is the colour of many environmental organisations (e.g., Greenpeace) and political parties in Europe (the Green Party). Second, yellow, which is associated with sunshine and therefore with energy and hope. And, finally, brown signifying the earth and/or the soil, usually symbolising resilience, neutrality, and security. All three colours correspond to the project's focus on a carbon-neutral, circular, and sustainable transition. The transient palette is also used to demonstrate the always evolving character of the project's ambition to co-create and co-develop pathways towards industrial climate neutrality, circularity, and sustainability.

The visual identity ensures consistent, professional, and communicative outreach towards industry, policy, and academic audiences, facilitating Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) activities, both internally (in all project communications) and externally (in all synergies or other related activities and events).

Apart from the "Funded by the EU" logo, all TRANSIENCE visual identity promotion materials and document templates features the logo of Processes4Planet Partnership (or 'P4Planet', 'P4P', etc.), with which TRANSIENCE is affiliated. P4Planet is a European co-programmed Public-Private Partnership established between A.SPIRE—a private entity—and the European Commission, in the context of Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space) of the Horizon Europe funding programme.

2 The TRANSIENCE Logo

It is important to create a distinctive yet simple visual identity. Therefore, the official logo, as a central feature of the project's visual identity, is designed to reflect the project's clear and inclusive orientation.

Figure 1. The official TRANSIENCE logo

The logo is included in all project documentation (paper/printed or electronic), including any promotional materials related to TRANSIENCE. This final version of the project's logo (Figure 1) has been selected from several other options discussed with the consortium partners (as presented in ANNEX I).

2.1 Graphical Charter

Following the finalisation of the logo, a graphical charter was created to provide the specific guidelines that must be followed for all purposes. These guidelines concern the logo size and colours (Figure 2), minimum clear space, straplines' alignment, and use of the logo against various backgrounds (Figure 3). These specifications are also shown in ANNEX II.

The TRANSIENCE Graphical Charter:

- introduces the final logo and provides the guidelines to be followed by all consortium partners to keep up with consistent branding in all project communications,
- provides the elements of visual identity for proper use and reproduction, and
- serves as a reference manual for application communications.

BASIC LOGO

COLOUR PALLETTE

Figure 2. Logo colours specifications

B/W & NEGATIVE LOGO

Figure 3. Logo use against various backgrounds

Furthermore, the selected logo typeface is shown in Figure 4.

FONT

AmpleSoft Pro (regular)

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z

AmpleSoft Pro (medium)

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z

Figure 4. Logo typeface

The digital version of the TRANSCIENCE graphical charter is available to download on the TRANSCIENCE website.

3 The TRANSIENCE Project Flyer

The flyer contains a brief overview of TRANSIENCE, designed to create visibility of the project's fundamental information (scope, objectives, etc.) and to inform of the consortium synthesis.

The project flyer size is A5 and includes three elements:

- a brief description of the project's scope and objectives,
- the TRANSIENCE consortium partners logos, and
- the project's contact details and social media channels.

The TRANSIENCE project flyer will be distributed at conferences, meetings, workshops, and other events to relevant academic, industry, and policy stakeholders, as well as to other synergy projects and/or organisations. The flyer has initially been produced in English but will be available in all consortium partner languages both electronically and in hard copy ahead of the first series of workshops (in the Basque Country, the port of Rotterdam, Rhine-Ruhr, and Silesia). The digital version of the TRANSIENCE flyer is available for download on the TRANSIENCE website.

The TRANSIENCE flyer is shown in Figure 5 and can also be found in ANNEX III in finer detail.

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Senior Research Associate
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General Information:
contact@transience.eu

www.transience.eu

Project Partners:

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 5. The TRANSIENCE Project Flyer

4 The TRANSCIENCE Project Leaflet

A promotional leaflet has been prepared for dissemination among academic researchers, the policy world, industry associations and clusters, civil society stakeholders, and all other interested parties at conferences and/or other scientific meetings, workshops, and project-relevant events. The leaflet briefly describes the project’s methodological approach, objectives, and expected results, and informs of the consortium synthesis of the project.

The leaflet is trifold and consists of six distinct panels/sections, including one cover panel with a brief description of the project’s ambition, one panel on the project’s objectives, one panel on the project’s approach (distinguishing four highly intertwined activity flows), one panel on expected results and industrial cluster case studies, one panel with the consortium synthesis (with all partners’ logos), and one panel with the project’s contact details and social media channels.

The leaflet has initially been produced in English but will be translated to all consortium partners’ languages, in time for the first series of stakeholder workshops. It will be available both in hard copy and electronically. The digital version of the TRANSCIENCE leaflet is available for download on the project’s website.

The TRANSCIENCE leaflet size is A4. The leaflet can be shown in Figure 6 and can also be found in ANNEX IV in finer detail.

Figure 6. The TRANSCIENCE Project Leaflet

5 The TRANSCIENCE Project Poster

A publicity poster template has also been created, to be used as promotional material at physical or online events organised by the consortium partners, hosted by other relevant organisations and consortia, or hosted by the European Commission (e.g., COP side-events, Processes4Planet and Hubs4Circularity activities, and regional energy modelling platforms, such as the ECEMP, IAMC, etc.).

The poster includes:

- a quick glance at the TRANSCIENCE concept and objectives,
- partners' logos, and
- contact Information.

The poster will be further modified and updated as needed to allow new information to be included in line with the project's progress.

The digital version of the TRANSCIENCE poster can be found in two versions, in A3 and A0, to be used according to the needs of each event. Both versions are available for download on the project's website.

The TRANSCIENCE project poster is shown in Figure 7 and can also be found in ANNEX V in finer detail.

TRANSCIENCE
TRANSitioning towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry

The TRANSCIENCE project supports the creation of an open, integrated, modular framework to simulate pathways toward achieving the transition of European industries to climate neutrality, also addressing material efficiency, circular economy, and broader sustainability measures. It will develop interfaces among a diverse series of climate, energy, and industrial models along with novel conceptualisations of industrial circularity performance, and decarbonisation.

The project will be entirely open, co-developed, and validated from industry, policy, and civil society stakeholders, establishing a vibrant community of practice on industry-academia collaboration, promoting industrial best practice, and informing assessments, and transition strategies, at EU and country level, at global level, and within 4 heterogeneous regional industry clusters in Europe, to ensure their usability and exploitation in real-world use cases.

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www.transience.eu

Project Partners:

Figure 7. The TRANSCIENCE Project Poster

6 The TRANSCIENCE Project Roll-up Banner

A roll-up banner has been created for events organised by consortium partners or hosted by relevant stakeholder organisations and other interested parties. Both the logo and the project's ambition are displayed on the top. The poster is consistent with the project's visual identity. Contact details and social media channels are placed in the middle and all consortium partners' logos are presented towards the bottom.

The size of the TRANSCIENCE project roll-up banner is 85 cm x 200 cm.

The banner is portable and has its own retracting mechanism built from aluminium, which enables easy portability and setup. Aluminium banners are a popular eco-friendly option, primarily because of their ability to be easily recycled.

The TRANSCIENCE project poster includes four elements:

- the logo and title of the project,
- a brief description of the project's concept,
- partners' logos, and
- the project's contact details and social media channels.

The digital version of the TRANSCIENCE roll-up banner is available for download on the project's website. It is also shown in Figure 8 and can also be found in ANNEX VI in finer detail.

TRANSIENCE

**TRANSITIONing towards
an Efficient, carbon-Neutral
Circular European industry**

The TRANSIENCE project supports the creation of an open, integrated, modular framework to simulate pathways toward achieving the transition of European industries to climate neutrality. It will develop interfaces among a diverse series of climate, energy, and industrial models along with novel conceptualisations of industrial circularity performance and decarbonisation.

The project will be entirely open, co-developed, and validated from industry, policy, and civil society stakeholders, establishing industry-academia collaboration, promoting industrial best practice, and informing assessments and transition strategies at EU and country level, at global level, and within 4 heterogeneous regional industry clusters in Europe.

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www.transience.eu

Project Partners:

Figure 8. The TRANSIENCE Project Roll-up Banner

7 The TRANSIENCE Project Presentation

A project presentation has been created containing basic project information. More specifically, the presentation includes a cover with the project logo and description, a page with all basic project information, a map of where each consortium partner is situated, a page with the key project objectives, and a final page with the project logo and social media channels.

With appropriate adaptations, it will be used by consortium partners as the main project presentation tool for dissemination purposes in project relevant events.

The TRANSIENCE project presentation will work as a template to be regularly updated and adapted by consortium partners according to their specific needs, although the basic project information (including the project's funding and affiliation logos) will be displayed on all occasions.

The digital version of the TRANSIENCE project presentation is available for download on the TRANSIENCE website.

The presentation template cover is shown in Figure 9 and it can be found in full detail in ANNEX VII.

Figure 9. The TRANSIENCE Project Presentation cover

8 The TRANSCIENCE Project Website

The TRANSCIENCE website will serve, according to the DoA, as a constant node of dissemination and engagement and a reference site with materials (deliverables, visuals, briefs, papers, etc.) and useful links related to industrial decarbonisation and circularity performance, climate action, sustainability, and the EU's transition to net-zero, as well as to relevant initiatives, actors, consortia, and projects.

The project website will provide information on the structure, scope, consortium, Scientific Advisory Board, synergies, completed and upcoming events, and all other news of the TRANSCIENCE project, as well as links to all project deliverables and publications. The website will also summarise and update progress toward the final model framework produced (MIC3), as well as the satellite modules comprising it (including the online interface tool for non-expert use). The development of the website is essential to the effective promotion of the project's concept, activities, results, and stakeholder engagement. All project outcomes and results will be published online. The website will provide links for further details and dedicated data-sharing workspaces, where all project results will also be disseminated.

There are two domain names of the project's website, which can be accessed at <https://www.transience.eu> and <https://www.industry4netzero.eu>. These domain names contain the .eu extension denoting their European origin. The selected wording for both domains directly fulfil the primary requirements of successful domain names: they are descriptive and easy to remember.

The website is built in Drupal, which is a free, open-source content management system (CMS).

The website will measure and monitor the visitors' behaviour, via a connection with the Google Analytics service. The data insights coming from the TRANSCIENCE website can be accessed directly from the Google Analytics interface.

8.1 Design

In terms of design, the website will be as clear and as accessible as possible, reflecting the inclusive approach of TRANSCIENCE. The website's colour palette is directly in line with the project logo and overall visual identity of the project. The website's design is clean and light, utilising contrasting colours to distinguish the text from the background and make reading easier on the eye. Also, the website showcases the project's industry focus using stock photos of European Energy-Intensive Industries (EII). A contrasting dark green banner towards the bottom of the website vividly highlights the project's communication details (e-mail, newsletter subscription, social media channels), visually separating the website's footer, where the project's basic info, funding details and affiliations are displayed. The header of the project's website is kept light to clearly guide visitors through the website's content. The typeface used across all sections of the website is mostly kept simple to avoid distracting visitors, while always remaining consistent with the project's visual identity.

Regarding technical implementation, the website is developed using responsive web design, enabling access from different screen sizes and devices. The website uses Cookies to enhance visitors' surfing and browsing, while Google Analytics is used to monitor the project

communication through the website as well as produce anonymised statistics of the website's visitor activity. TRANSCIENCE implements IP anonymisation (removing the final octet of the IP address before storing it) to prevent the collection of person-identifying information. Browser settings and add-ons are utilised to enable users to disable both cookies and Google Analytics tracking. Also, website users are given the option to reject the use of cookies by clicking on a pop-up upon their initial website visit. Detailed information concerning Cookies and Google Analytics and their application and manipulation is provided in the website's Privacy and Cookies Policy.

Overall, the TRANSCIENCE website follows modern web design principles and focuses primarily on usability, accessibility, and straightforward navigation. Search engine optimisation is further improved by posting several news items with appropriate keywords on a frequent basis.

Several design updates and improvements are anticipated in the coming months. The website's stock photos will be gradually updated and replaced with images chosen from the project's four industrial cluster case studies to better portray the project's aim to address real-world use cases; these images will be taken during workshops with stakeholders and other project-related events. The WP5/9/12 teams will always contact individuals appearing in images for consent before publishing the images online.

A preview of the website's Home page is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. The TRANSCIENCE Website Home page

8.2 Structure and Content

The TRANSCIENCE website can be navigated via the main menu displayed in the website's header at the top part of every webpage. The project website's main menu includes six sections, aligned with the project logo. It consists of a two-level navigation menu that guides visitors in an intuitive manner. The website's main menu contains the following items (Figure 11):

Figure 11. TRANSCIENCE Website structure (site map)

- The TRANSCIENCE logo item directs the visitor to the Home page.
- The “About” menu item includes five sections that contain information about the project's concept, objectives, work structure, project consortium, and scientific advisory board.
- The “News & Events” menu item contains links to all posts about project news, policy events, workshops, and other events.
- The “MIC3 Platform” menu item includes a submenu to be configured and updated along with the development of the MIC3 framework and all satellite modules comprising it. Currently, the “MIC3 Platform” item contains a brief description of the MIC3 framework, an infographic demonstrating the project's model development flow, and six fields describing the approach of each satellite module (socioeconomic, product/end-use, material, industrial, energy system, and environmental).
- The “Synergies” section will be devoted to all documents and activities (e.g., papers, briefs, events, etc.) that will be jointly carried out with other relevant research projects and/or initiatives. It includes a “Scientific Publications” and a “Conferences” item with a brief description, basic information, and the link to these documents and/or activities. At the bottom of the “Synergies” page, the “News and Events” section is also included, to inform visitors of the project's updates.
- The “Publications” menu contains five items: “Scientific Publications”, which will primarily

disseminate the project’s peer-reviewed papers to the research/academic community and will feature a copiable APA citation; “Conferences”, where the project’s results presented in academic venues will be outlined, again featuring an APA citation; “Policy Briefs”, highlighting all policy recommendations deriving from the project; “Industry Guides”, showcasing the industry-relevant prescriptions for both the regional industrial clusters and European industry in general; and, finally, the project’s “Deliverables” item, which will provide consolidated and up-to-date access to all project deliverables. The content for each of these items is displayed with a dropdown layout. All materials in these sections will be available to download and will also be disseminated through the project’s social media channels.

- The “Communication” menu item also includes five sections: “Newsletters and Press Releases”, incorporating selected project news, inputs from all consortium partners, progress and key outcomes of the project, and a GDPR-compliant subscription service; “Videos”, used for disseminating TRANSCIENCE results in a more effective way to appropriate audiences; “Infographics”, displaying interactive or static infographics for better visualisation of the project’s results; “Media/Press”, with an overview of all project-related media coverage in non-scientific press; and “Visual Identity”, containing all project promotional information and materials (see Sections 1-7 above). All content displayed in this section will also be regularly shared via the TRANSCIENCE social media channels (LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Instagram, BlueSky, and Mastodon).

8.3 Main Elements of the Website Pages

Each TRANSCIENCE website page consists of three main design parts:

- the Header (at the top),
- the Footer (bottom), and
- the Content (in between).

8.3.1 Header

The Header, as shown in Figure 12, contains the project logo (which also directs users to the website’s home page), the navigation main menu, and the search tool/bar. The same Header remains consistent in all webpages and is always visible at the top as users scroll down the page.

Figure 12. The TRANSCIENCE Website Header

8.3.2 Footer

The Footer, as shown in Figure 13, includes three sections of information: the left section contains the TRANSCIENCE logo (which when clicked returns the visitor to the website’s home page); details about the project’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions Programme funding, accompanied by the required disclaimer (concerning the project’s authors views and opinions); and a notice of the project’s affiliation to the Processes4Planet Partnership. The right section

contains a menu with Quick Links (currently showing Concept, Project Consortium, and Contact page links that may be updated later), the name and affiliation of the ICCS contact (Project Coordinator), and a link to the Privacy & Cookies Policy.

Figure 13. The TRANSCIENCE Website Footer

8.3.3 Home Page

The Home page, shown in Figure 10, consists of nine sections that attract interest and provide visitors with an overview of the project’s various aspects. The website’s home page is accessed by clicking on the TRANSCIENCE logo in the main menu.

1st Section: Header

Please see section 8.3.1 “Header”.

2nd Section: Description

This section contains the TRANSCIENCE logo and a brief description of the project. A “Learn More” arrow directs visitors to the “About” menu.

Figure 14. The TRANSCIENCE Website "Description" section

3rd Section: ‘At a Glance’ & ‘Publications’

This section, as shown in Figure 15, will capture visitors’ interest with two banners featuring key metrics related to TRANSCIENCE. The top “At a Glance” banner showcases the project’s lifetime in months and other basic data (consortium partners, modelling modules, case studies).

The bottom “Publications” banner showcases (with bold, animated, running numbers) the project’s progress and dissemination through scientific publications, conferences, policy briefs, and media

articles.

Figure 15. The TRANSCIENCE Website "At a Glance" and "Publication" section

4th Section: News & Events

This section, as shown in Figure 16, contains links to selected project news and events. By clicking on each item, the visitor is directed to the corresponding webpage. A "View More" button at the bottom directs visitors to the main menu section "News & Events".

Figure 16. The TRANSCIENCE Website "News & Events" section

5th Section: Concept

This section, as shown in Figure 17, showcases the project's concept and contains four items that indicate the project's key methodological approaches (Conceptualise, Engage, Develop, and Transform), briefly described when clicked.

Figure 17. The TRANSCIENCE Website "Concept" section

6th Section: Regional Clusters

This section, shown in Figure 18, showcases an overview of the project’s four regional industrial clusters. By clicking the arrows on the left or the right side, a different cluster is showcased. Each description contains a map, thumbnails of existing industrial sectors with a brief description, key figures concerning the socioeconomic status of each region (population, GDP, and employment), and the industrial sectors in numbers.

Figure 18. The TRANSCIENCE Website "Regional Clusters" section

7th Section: Consortium Partners

This section, shown in Figure 19, includes the twelve partners involved in the TRANSCIENCE consortium. Each partner is represented by its official logo that, when clicked, opens a brief

description tab.

Figure 19. The TRANSCIENCE Website "Consortium Partners" section

8th Section: Subscription banner (Sign up to our newsletter)

A subscription banner ("Sign up to our newsletter"), as shown in Figure 20, is displayed on every webpage just above the footer section. The project's transient colour palette makes the subscription banner stand out from the webpage content and footer. Users can subscribe to the TRANSCIENCE newsletter by entering an e-mail address and an organisational affiliation and completing a CAPTCHA verification and a Privacy Policy agreement. The banner also contains links to the project's social media channels.

Figure 20. The TRANSCIENCE Website "Subscription" section

9th Section: Footer

Please see section 8.3.2 "Footer".

8.3.4 Other Pages

The rest of the TRANSCIENCE webpages (also called 'inside pages'), can be categorised into static content pages and dynamic content pages. A static content page usually contains information that typically remains the same throughout the project (e.g., Concept, Objectives, Work Structure, Project Consortium, and Scientific Advisory Board), whereas a dynamic page contains information that is frequently updated (e.g., News & Events, MIC3 Platform, Synergies, Publications, and Communication).

An example of a static page is shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. The TRANSCIENCE Website “Project Consortium” page

An example of a dynamic page is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. The TRANSIENCE Website "Newsletters & Press Releases" page

ANNEX I: TRANSCIENCE Alternative logos

OTHER VERSIONS

ANNEX II: TRANSIENCE Logo/Colour Specifications

BASIC LOGO

COLOUR PALLETE

RGB: 0-104-56
#006838

RGB: 191-98-43
#bfc62b

RGB:149-121-45
#95792d

B/W & NEGATIVE LOGO

ANNEX III: TRANSIENCE Project Flyer

TRANSITIONING towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry

The TRANSIENCE project supports the creation of an open, integrated, modular framework to simulate pathways toward achieving the transition of European industries to climate neutrality, also addressing material efficiency, circular economy, and broader sustainability measures. It will develop interfaces among a diverse series of climate, energy, and industrial models along with novel conceptualisations of industrial circularity performance, and decarbonisation.

The project will be entirely open, co-developed, and validated from industry, policy, and civil society stakeholders, establishing a vibrant community of practice on industry-academia collaboration, promoting industrial best practice, and informing assessments, and transition strategies, at EU and country level, at global level, and within 4 heterogeneous regional industry clusters in Europe, to ensure their usability and exploitation in real-world use cases.

Let's stay connected

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Project Partners:

ANNEX IV: TRANSIENCE Project Leaflet

The TRANSIENCE project supports the creation of an open, integrated, modular framework to simulate pathways toward achieving the transition of European industries to climate neutrality, also addressing material efficiency, circular economy, and broader sustainability measures. It will develop interfaces among a diverse series of climate, energy, and industrial models along with novel conceptualisations of industrial circularity performance and decarbonisation.

Objectives

TRANSIENCE aims to:

- Achieve model enhancement and integration to develop a new, fully integrated model, the Model for European Industry Circularity and Climate Change mitigation (MIC3).
- Investigate the interplays, co-benefits, and trade-offs between decarbonisation, circularity, and sustainability of European industry.
- Provide policy advice and promote best practice in industry.
- Promote transparency, openness, and legitimacy, by implementing open science principles and documenting new modelling capacity for expert and non-expert audiences.
- Reinforce the role of all stakeholders, co-developing model capabilities, co-designing research questions, legitimising the implementation process, and validating results.
- Enhance the exploitation potential of results and recommendations, and build capacity across academia and industry.

Approach

Conceptualise

This component characterises the diversity of available and prospective decarbonisation and circular economy policies, technologies, opportunities, and risks, before reviewing how current models can represent these, and understand the research capacities needed to develop state-of-the-art typology and databases. Bottom-up analytical techniques are used to capture the costs and potential to reduce energy-and carbon-intensive materials, energy use, and carbon emissions. These insights will be enriched with an analysis of EU industrial competitiveness in the global context and a series of sociotechnical analyses from a systems of innovation perspective, aiming to drive the project's model development and data management strategy.

Engage

Here, a strategy and database are developed for continuous, vivid stakeholder engagement with EU and national policymakers, EU industry associations, representatives of the selected regional industrial clusters, the modelling community, and civil society. Existing capacities are discussed to foster expectations and gain perspectives of technical requirements to develop MIC3, to co-design the most pertinent questions to be mapped onto the developed modules, allowing stakeholders to validate their performance and usability. Finally, industry and policy stakeholder needs will be translated into scenario frameworks to co-produce pathways of European industrial transformation towards net-zero and give stakeholders the chance to validate MIC3 and exploit the new toolbox.

Develop

This component entails the development of standalone modules that correspond to the needs identified in the previous two components, including a socioeconomic module, a service and product database, a series of material flow modules for Europe and the globe,

a series of industrial modules for the European Economic Area (EEA), a dedicated energy system module at the national level for the 27-member bloc and associated countries, and an environmental impact assessment module. After their validation, the modules will be fully integrated into the MIC3 framework, also leading to the development of a simplified version to be released online and facilitate non-expert use.

Transform

This component collects and maps stakeholders overarching questions onto the new modules, towards carrying out case study scenario exercises to demonstrate each module's capabilities for stakeholders to validate. Following the finalisation of these individual modules and the development of the new framework, MIC3 will be used to assess the transformation of European industries towards a circular economic net-zero future by 2050 and broader sustainable development.

Expected Results

TRANSIENCE will create a technology-rich, open-source integrated assessment model, MIC3, featuring sectoral and national levels, to simulate pathways towards industrial decarbonisation, high circularity, and overall sustainability in Europe. MIC3 will comprise several interconnected modules drawing on different perspectives, and modelling paradigms, covering a broad time horizon. All models and pathways will be co-created and validated by policymakers, industries, researchers, and civil society, and will be used to develop databases of transformative policies, technologies, services, and products for industrial transition within four industrial clusters (Germany, Spain, the Netherlands, and Poland) and specific sectors in the EU, with a focus on energy-intensive and process industries. The project will also produce reports exploring links between circularity and decarbonisation, including a conceptual framework, examples of such links, and interactions with global competitiveness, innovation, and sustainability. An open science toolbox for modelling development will also be created to facilitate non-expert use.

Project Partners

Let's stay connected

**TRANSITIONING towards
an Efficient, carbon-Neutral
Circular European industry**

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ANNEX V: TRANSCIENCE Project Poster

TRANSCIENCE

TRANSITIONING towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry

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The project will be entirely open, co-developed, and validated from industry, policy, and civil society stakeholders, establishing a vibrant community of practice on industry-academia collaboration, promoting industrial best practice, and informing assessments, and transition strategies, at EU and country level, at global level, and within 4 heterogeneous regional industry clusters in Europe, to ensure their usability and exploitation in real-world use cases.

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- [transienceproject.bsky.social](#)

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Project Partners:

ANNEX VI: TRANSIENCE Project Roll-up Banner

TRANSITIONING towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry

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Project Partners:

ANNEX VII: TRANSCIENCE Project Presentation

TRANSITIONING TOWARDS AN EFFICIENT,
CARBON-NEUTRAL CIRCULAR EUROPEAN
INDUSTRY

ATHENS KICK-OFF MEETING (KOM)
8-9 SEPTEMBER 2022

TRANSCIENCE project overview

Dr. Alexandros Nikas (ICCS)

www.transcience.eu

Overview

Title: Transitioning towards an efficient, carbon-neutral circular European industry

Funding: HORIZON EUROPE, RIA, Research and Innovation Action

Lifetime: January 2024 - January 2028 (48 months)

Coordination: ICCS, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems

Participants: 12 Consortium Partners

Call/Grant: HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-36

Consortium

Objectives

- O₁. Achieve model enhancement and integration
- O₂. Investigate the interplays, co-benefits and trade-offs between decarbonisation, circularity and sustainability of European industry
- O₃. Provide policy advice and promote best practice in industry
- O₄. Promote transparency, openness and legitimacy
- O₅. Reinforce the role of all stakeholders
- O₆. Enhance exploitation and capacity development

Thank you!

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